

WP7 Communications Plan: D7.1 (D31)

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Summary of Communications Plan

This document WP7 Communications Plan: D7.1 (D31) outlines progress in our communications up to now, and the strategy that will be implemented in the Horizon 2020 project "TiPES: Tipping Points in the Earth System". The strategy provides an overview of the key stakeholders that will be engaged and the outreach and dissemination activities that will be applied. We hope that this plan will ensure that communications will be considered at the core of the project objectives, and will contribute to the final achievements of the project by being a proactive, rather than stand-alone reactive endeavour.

We foresee that effective TiPES communications can:

- help us achieve our overall project objectives;
- engage effectively with stakeholders – such as policymakers, journalists and general public;
- demonstrate the importance and impact of our work, with effective collaboration with the scientific community and with science communicators;
- eventually lead to a change in behaviour and perceptions, and this will be important for future trends and practices in industry and business.

Our strategy is built on three pillars which address policymakers, the scientific community and the broader public. We will also seek to engage audiences from business, industry and NGOs through considered discussions with their specific representatives. First steps have been taken since the start of TiPES in September 2019, and the foundation of each pillar has been laid. For the communication with policymakers, contacts with the relevant ministries in Switzerland and Denmark have been established.

Furthermore, the importance of tipping points was underscored at the inaugural Science Lecture to the World Meteorological Organization, and official contacts with the new Science Director are made. Communication with the scientific community is carried out in the framework of large, international conferences. At the General Assembly of the European Geophysical Union in May 2020, four events will take place that have been organized by members of TiPES.

In addition, an information platform for scientific results from TiPES partners and their dissemination is established (www.tipes.dk). Channels on social media have also been developed. Finally, the broader public will receive information on tipping point science through a structured media plan that will reach both local and international audiences. Local activities at the partners' institutions will include an innovative 'game' that is based on interactive teaching of high school students. The game will also be available as an app, which itself reflects contemporary methods of student engagement and outreach.

Planned Contribution to the top level objectives of TiPES

The Communications strategy for TiPES is guided by the main project objectives and our communications activities will help reach these goals. Effective communications need to be at the core of the objectives in order to be effective, not working independently or in reaction to the goals. We will continue to consider each objective with an associated set of outcomes thus contributing to the achievements.

Objective 1 - Identify Tipping Elements (TEs) and their interactions in models and data:

This will mostly be achieved through peer-to-peer science communication moderated through the activities of published articles and datasets, conferences and specialised workshops and discussions. The workshops will be key events for building strategies for collaboration. We have scheduled our first workshop in Denmark in June 2020 with both internal (TiPES) and external (other science partners) delegates. This format, encouraging science dissemination and collaboration will continue over the duration of TiPES.

Objective 2-Provide approaches for the identification and validation of Early Warning Signals

The presentation of the latest science results and the exchange with the scientific community at EGU's 2020 General Assembly, in particular the events organized and convened by TiPES scientists, will contribute to this objective. We will aim to be proactive in our media plans ahead of such conferences, with prepared press releases, detailing new results or newsworthy published articles. This will be based on clearly thought-through 'take-home' messages for journalists, and scientists will be prepared in order to gain far reaching balanced coverage of results to the general public.

Objective 3-Characterise climate response in the presence of Tipping Points (TPs)

Here, analyses of climate model simulations, specifically in the CMIP6 effort, carried out by TiPES scientists will provide key information on impacts of tipping points and crossing of thresholds. Again, our media and science strategy will be applied here to ensure engagement of stakeholders such as the science community and general public.

Objective 4-Define and identify safe operating spaces

At this stage of TiPES, the safe operating space to avoid tipping points, is not yet outlined.

Objective 5-Bridge the gap between climate science and policy advice

By bringing tipping points to the attention of policymakers via meetings at the ministerial level in Switzerland and Denmark, we have taken a first important step towards addressing the gap and provide ideas how to bridge it. Proactive engagement of policymakers at the ministerial level and with IPCC Focal Points is a key element of our strategy.

Dissemination and exploitation of TiPES results

Reaching Specific Audiences

The science outcomes of TiPES will have far reaching impacts, that will affect a wide range of groups. The audiences we plan to engage, in order to raise awareness and understanding of ‘tipping points in of likely include:

- The wider public: ‘news readers’
 - Three categories of news readers: traditionalists (who use traditional print and broadcast news primarily), netnewsters (who seek and acquire almost all of their news content from the internet and social media), and integrators (who seek information in both places).
- Science and research practitioners
- Media
- Policymakers and intergovernmental organisations
- Business and Industry
- Schools and Educators

Expected Dissemination Activities

Table 1: Here we present a list of key activities, categorised by audience

Type of Audience	Type of dissemination activity	Name of the scientist (institution), title of the presentation, event	Place and date of the event	Estimated number of persons reached
WMO leadership, country delegates, program leaders of WCRP, stakeholders	Inaugural Science Lecture of WMO	Thomas Stocker (UBERN), Title: The climate of tomorrow: Building knowledge for Earth stewardship	WMO, Geneva, 8.5.2019	ca. 150 (direct) unknown (webcast)
Minister, General Secretariat of ministry	Personal briefing of Swiss Minister of Environment, Transport, Energy and Communication	Thomas Stocker (UBERN)	Bern, 1.11.2019	10

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Public	Social media	Science Project Mgrs: Eliza Cook, Helle Kjær Journalist: Henrik Prætorius(UCPH)	Online, ongoing activities	International
Public	Podcasts	Production of podcasts. Organized by Henrik Prætorius	3 already published. More to follow. General public	International audience. Expected reach: 5000
Public/Media	Media releases	David Trads, Peter Ditlevsen	Both to general and scientific audience	International
Public	Popular science events and talks	David Trads, Peter Ditlevsen	TiPES will organize event at 'Folkemødet' in June 2020, a popular event for Danish politicians, science dissemination etc.	More than 100.000 participate. We expect 100 for our talk.
Media	Dedicated press invitations to meetings/ conferences when we have results	David Trads, Peter Ditlevsen	This will begin in 2020.	International
Business/ Industry	Tailored interview with industry and business representatives	Marcello Petitta	Teleconference meetings	5 industrial /business representatives
Businesses/ Industry	Presence at some key conventions	Marcello Petitta	May, 2021	5/10 industrial /business representatives
Schools	Interactive game as a teaching resource	FABULA Studios	Before end 2023	Danish national level

TiPES Stakeholder Engagement and Progress so far

Contribution to task T7.1:

UBERN has participated in a closed-door meeting on November 1, 2019, with the Swiss Minister of Environment, Transport, Energy and Communication, Mrs. S. Sommaruga, during which the most pressing national challenges in reaching the Paris Agreement and the UN Sustainable Development Goals were discussed. In this conversation, tipping points in the Earth System and the increasing danger to cross thresholds was illustrated with some recent results from the scientific community. It was also stated that currently the knowledge of policymakers on this important aspect of anthropogenic climate change with potentially dangerous impacts is

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insufficient. This is due to the lack of a comprehensive assessment of the science on tipping points. For example, some argue that tipping points are imminent and therefore geoengineering should be seriously considered as an emergency intervention. Equally problematic is the view that the climate system is very stable and will therefore naturally recover from perturbations. Decisions by policymakers under such conditions lack the scientific basis. This will be followed up with the Secretariat of the Minister and the relevant Swiss federal agency.

UCPH has arranged a meeting with the Danish Minister of Climate, Energy and Utilities, Mr. D. Jorgensen at which also UBERN will participate. At this meeting in Copenhagen on March 27, 2020 similar topics will be discussed. In particular, we will present the idea of requesting from the IPCC a Special Report on Tipping Points in its next assessment cycle, which will begin in 2022.

Contribution to task T7.2:

At the inaugural Science Lecture of the World Meteorological Organization, held by T. Stocker from UBERN on May 8, 2019, Tipping Points were addressed and the timeliness of WMO requesting an IPCC Special Report on Tipping Points was emphasized. The audience was the leadership of WMO (including the Secretary General and the Science Director), delegates of a number of countries including IPCC Focal Points, project leaders of the World Climate Research Programme and various stakeholders.

The lecture is summarized at <https://public.wmo.int/en/media/news/wmo-starts-public-science-lecture-series>

Contribution to task T7.4:

A widely available report announcing the start of TiPES has been published in *Eos* (Blaustein, R., 2019, Scientists announce TiPES project, *Eos*, 100, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019EO121561>). Up to now, four peer reviewed papers have been published and 17 are submitted.

Contribution to task T7.5:

Regarding outreach to the scientific community, TiPES has already made an appearance at the 2019 General Assembly of the European Geophysical Union with the contribution "Tipping Points in the Earth System: An introduction to the TiPES project" by B. Goswami (PIK) and all PIs from TiPES.

TiPES has played a very active role in shaping the program of the upcoming General Assembly of the European Geophysical Union that will be held in Vienna in May 2020. Members of TiPES have proposed, and were granted four events, three scientific sessions and one splinter meeting:

1. ITS3.1/NP1.2 Tipping Points in the Earth System, Including Lewis Fry Richardson Medal Lecture, co-convened by Niklas Boers (PIK), Peter Ditlevsen (UCPH), and others.

2. SC4.23 Meet the NP officers: Thoughts on Nonlinear Processes in Geosciences, co-convened by T. Alberti, Niklas Boers (PIK), and others.
3. NP1.1 Mathematics of Planet Earth, co-convened by Valerio Lucarini (UR), Peter Ashwin (UEXE), Niklas Boers (PIK), Vera Melinda Galfi, Michel Crucifix (UCL), and others
4. SMI4 TiPES, convened by Peter Ditlevsen

It should also be noted that the recipient of the 2020 Lewis Fry Richardson Medal is Valerio Lucarini of UR, a partner of TiPES. Congratulations to Valerio for this prestigious recognition!

On the dedicated website for TiPES (www.tipes.dk) publications are accessible as they are published, and efforts to release associated podcasts and media releases for some publications have taken place with the aim of widening the dissemination of the results.

Expected Results and Outcomes

With the three pillars of communication we have firmly established the position of TiPES in the information landscape.

We have initiated, at the ministerial level, a conversation about the importance of tipping points in the process of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and for the UN SDGs. Furthermore, we have engaged a key UN organization, the WMO, to participate in this conversation. It will be continued with the goal to work out a specific proposal for an IPCC Special Report on "*Climate Tipping Points and Consequences for Habitability and Resources*".

We have started a series of activities convening the scientific community at the most important professional meeting in Europe, the General Assembly of the European Geophysical Union. TiPES will employ this venue every year during the project duration.

Plan for progress beyond the state of the art – Contributing to Policymaking

To our knowledge, it is the first time that an EU Project engages in a conversation directly at the ministerial level. This direct science-policymaker contact and interaction can be a key to shaping future assessments carried out by intergovernmental bodies such as the IPCC. It is a most effective way to collect, assess, and communicate robust science information to policymakers and eventually to the public. From such an assessment, that TiPES has initiated, we expect to provide clear, robust and accessible statements about tipping points, probability of occurrence, and estimates of impacts that can be put to use by policymakers and that illustrate to the public the risk associated with tipping.

It is the goal of WP7 to continue this avenue and seek to include at an early stage the European Union with its progressive position regarding addressing the climate crisis, and to other partner countries of TiPES.

Media Engagement Strategy

How will this strategy contribute to the expected impacts of TiPES?

Obtaining balanced and credible media coverage of our most unique findings will be key to opening up the debate about tipping points and informing various groups about the pressing challenges that we will face as a society in the future.

Accordingly, we have allocated appropriate resources with communication experts. Here is an outline of the communications plan for the project:

Reaching the different audiences

1. **General Public: 'News Readers:'** Reached through a variety of media platforms, including our own website content, our own podcasts, as well as through mainstream magazine stories and local and international news pieces, and a strong presence on social media.
2. **Journalists and science communicators:** Reached through social media, television, radio and online-broadsheet print. Among other initiatives through press events at our workshops/conferences and with press releases, press briefings and direct contacts.
3. **Science community:** Peer-to-peer engagement through collaboration and workshops, conferences and published papers. Social media will also play a role.
4. **Children and young:** Engaged through and interactive game and targeted media. This special outreach is a key component of our communications strategy as it is a new target group to reach.
5. **Primary school teachers:** As we would like to reach out to children of primary school age especially, we plan to conduct special workshops with the Training-of-Trainers model in which our experts give school teachers a special knowledge of climate and tipping points.

Levels of Media Engagement – Local vs International

1. **Local level in Danish media:** As the TiPES-project has its main leadership at the University of Copenhagen we will target local media with stories of special, local impact.
2. **Local level in other TiPES partners in their home countries:** Each participating partner will need to do their own local media outreach through their traditional contact. An example is the Netherlands' national news channel NPO
3. **International media:** TiPES is a pan-European and international research project and, accordingly, our primary media outreach will be international media. All Tipping Points are transnational, which is key to our communications.

Media sectors

1. **Local interest:** It is key to our communications strategy that we can address a general audience that is not particularly interested in neither climate change in general nor tipping points in particular. We want to engage this group through local interest.
2. **Science and environment:** Obviously we plan to communicate through well-known established media platforms in this important sector. We will target specific media.
3. **Political and financial:** New science results and findings need to reach both politicians and businesses. Accordingly, we will identify and reach out to media that attracts these two key groups, such as financial newspapers and TV-stations.
4. **New and green technology:** There is a whole new group of new media platforms, sometimes independent, other times part of an organization or business, that deal directly with new, green and sustainable technologies. We will identify those.

Engaging journalists from different sectors

1) Print media

- **Local:** In each participating country we will reach out to local, important journalists, in particular those with special interest in the environment/climate. Thankfully they grow in numbers. In Denmark that could be the dailies such as Politiken, Information, Jyllands-Posten, Berlingske.
- **International:** In order to reach international audiences, we will spend resources on media that devotes a lot of time to the environment/climate. For instance, but not limited to, the Guardian, Financial Times and El País in Europe and New York Times, Washington Post and others globally.
- **Magazine:** As we know magazines, weekly and monthly, are best for background and analysis, we will specifically reach out to them. That could be New Scientist, the Economist, National Geographic and others.

2) Online

- Digital media, often very topic specific media, including science blogs and sites, can serve as both direct communication to key stakeholders in the science community, but also as indirect communication to the general public.
- Besides the well-known sites – such as the BBC and the Guardian, that both have dedicated sections on the topic – we will reach out to important, but lesser known sites, including, but not limited to, climatedesk.com and earther.com.
- We will also establish our own webpage for the general public. It is already in a beta-version, but will be up and running during the summer of 2020. It will be hosted and run out of the University of Copenhagen.

3) Television and radio

- **Local:** In each country we will target the most important, local TV- and radio stations. In Denmark, for example, that would be DR, TV2, Radio4.
- **International:** We will as part of our international outreach target the BBC and Euronews amongst other channels, with the aim of being mentioned in their science, politics and business newscasts, blogs, etc
- **Documentary makers:** As a lot of the climate/tipping points research is more long term than now and here (newscasts) we will specifically target interesting producers of documentaries in order to try to get them interested in the topic.

How to engage with media

1) Reactive strategies

- We must be ready to answer sudden calls by different types of journalists – from those who know a lot about environmental and climate issues as well as generalists who just happen to cover the story of the day.
- In order to prepare our scientists for this important task our own communication experts, based in Copenhagen, will conduct special media training. One such event has already taken place. More will follow.

2) Proactive strategies

- **Workshops and Conferences:** We plan to invite both local and international journalists for workshops and conferences. We already had on in Paris, and we will have at least two in Vienna and Tromsø this year. Journalists will be given exclusive access to our scientist.
- **Our Published Papers:** Whenever new papers (with clear take-home messages) are published, we will try to direct their results and the scientists behind them to specific either local or more likely international journalists in order to maximize the impact.
- **Draft press releases:** We will aid the scientists with outreach to media when they have newsworthy articles coming. We will brief scientists on how to handle media questions, and, most importantly, to drive through their main message.
- **Social media:** We have already set up a Twitter-handle and we will also be present on Facebook and Instagram. This is a very important task, as we believe this will be a powerful tool to reach the general public. We will also train scientists to update regularly on our social media platforms.
- **Website:** We will further develop our own website in English that is already available in a beta-version. This will serve a dual purpose: One section for general public, one section for the scientific community. This will also operate as the landing page for all the material we will publish on social media.
- **Podcasts:** We plan to publish a number of podcasts (three have already been published) on topics related to TiPES. They will have a tone of voice that will make them easy to understand for the general public.

- **Schools:** As we have identified children and youth as a specific and very important target ground, our outreach here is of particular importance. In the fall of 2020 we will conduct a special workshop in Copenhagen for primary school teachers that we plan to move to other countries afterwards.
- **Promote the interactive game:** We are in the process of developing a specific online computer game for children and youth. The game will present various interactive scenarios linked to tipping points and tipping elements. Once that is available we will use our communications platforms to promote it

Strategy for Engaging Business and Industry

The business and industry sectors have already shown a strong interest in the TiPES project. Amigo is responsible for coordinating the flow of information from the scientific community to business and industrial sectors.

The idea is to invite representatives of some business/industrial sectors to the workshops organized during the TiPES project in order to collect, discuss and understand what the private sector expects from TiPES.

Amigo already contacted some private companies working in the following sectors:

- Insurance
- Energy production
- Air Transport
- Railway infrastructures
- Energy network

During 2020, Amigo and the project's partners will propose to select companies to participate as stakeholders in TiPES in order to collect the sectorial information needed.

After a first discussion with representatives of those sectors, Amigo collected a set of expected impacts which have been divided into two main categories:

1. Relationship between extreme events and tipping points. In particular, the industrial sector is interested to understand if it is possible to predict the approaching of tipping point in relationship to environmental extreme events.
2. The effects of tipping points on the industrial sector. The industrial sector is interested in understanding how their businesses will cope with the effects of tipping points, and how the associated changes will have an impact in their operational actions.

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In the first 24 month of the project, Amigo is planning to participate in at least 3 public events in which it will meet the above-mentioned stakeholders in order to propose specific interviews focused on the role of climate tipping points in the business and industrial sectors. Moreover, Amigo will prepare tailored online interviews with selected stakeholders.

Before the end of the project, a second series of interviews will be prepared in order to measure the impact of the project's results on the main aspects identified in the first interview round.

The results will be communicated and shared with each of the stakeholders selected.

The final objective is to link the business/industrial sector expectations and the results generated by TiPES. We will seek to identify the practical actions that will need to be employed by selected audiences.

Links that will be built with Other Projects

We plan to establish synergies with other projects:

In particular, with other EU projects; eg. [TiPACCS](#), [COMFORT](#), [EPICA Blue Action](#), [CRESCENDO](#) and EU clusters such as; [EU Polar cluster](#) and the EU climate modelling cluster.

And with those already specified in the proposal such as [PAGES](#), [Past Earth Network](#), RISE actions, [CMIPs](#) and [PMIPs Copernicus Climate Services](#), [CliMathNet](#), [MCRN](#), SIAM MPE, [CLIMCOR](#), [East-GRIP](#)

Green Deal Solutions: The EC requires policy feedback and the identification of the next pressing topics. There is a need for synergy between different fields such as modelling and earth observation, and we aim to develop links here.

Horizon Europe is the successor for H2020, and is the next 7-year plan. We are now looking for main research streams that should be developed with the aim to submit suggestions for consideration.